

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11846417>

CORRECTED MISTAKES IN THE WORK OF AMIR UMAR KHAN, SHAH AND POETIC ACTIVITY

Samatova Ismigul

A student of Karshi State University

Annotation: *In this article, the opinion that the works of the poet Amiri's pen were considered not his own, which was proven as a result of investigations and researches, is put forward. Also, the work of both the king and the poet will be reviewed and the opinions of many scientists and artists about Umar Khan will be compared.*

Key words: *Amiri, Fazli, "Majmuat ut-shuaro", court literature, shura era, royal-poetry series, Ergashali Shodiyev.*

Amirsaid Muhammad Umarchan - Amiriy Ko'kan is embodied in our eyes as a bright manifestation of the literary environment. At the end of the 18th century - the first half of the 20th century, it occupies the main place in the rapid growth of literary processes in Kok. It is no exaggeration to raise Amiri to a high rank as the leader of these processes. So, how was Amiri able to organize this literary process? First of all, he formed a scientific, cultural and literary environment. He was able to attract scientists, poets, teachers, painters and calligraphers from different regions to the city center. He led the opening of madrasahs and schools for many professions and the improvement of their activities. Amir Umar Khan's role in studying and copying many classical works, in addition to the development of translation works, in the creation, development and rise to the level of a unified reality of the literary environment of Kokand is incomparable.

Literature analysis and methodology

As a representative of the ruling class during the Shura period, Amiri's political activities and literary heritage were condemned. This was caused, on the one hand, by the requirements of the ideology of the time, and on the other hand, by insufficient critical view of literary sources. For example, Professor Ergashali Shodiyev, in his pamphlet "Fazliy Namangoniy and Khojand Poets", thinks about the artists around Amiri, mostly the poets of Khojand, and is skeptical about the poet's talent of the ruler. Such objectionable opinions appeared as a result of many of Amiri's ghazals being mistakenly attributed to Yusuf Amiri in various publications. Debates on this issue are still ongoing. This is primarily due to the fact that Yusuf Amiri's office has not yet been

found. But there are also issues of language and style. There is a time gap of three centuries between the two poets, one of whom lived in the 15th century and the other in the 18th century. During this period, Uzbek classical poetry underwent great changes in terms of language and style. Yusuf Amiri, like his contemporaries Lutfi, Atai, Hafiz Khorezmi and Gadoi, mainly followed the famous Persian-Tajik poet Kamal Khojandi. Amiri was tutored by Persian poets such as Lutfi, Navoi, Fuzuli, Mashrab, Zalili, Khoja Hafiz, Mavlona Jami, Mirzo Bedil, Saib Tabrizi, and studied at their school. The development of poetry during Yusuf Amiri's time cannot even be compared with that during Umar Khan's time. The fact that he chose Alisher Navoi, the great word artist who raised the status of Turkish poetry in world literature, and Mirza Abdulkadir Bedil, the innovative poet who revolutionized Persian poetry, as his teacher and tried to follow them, showed the level of Amiri's poetry. combs.

Discussion

Kokand Khan Umar Khan was also a worthy follower of the series of kings and poets. There are two views on it. Academician Aziz Qayumov writes about this: "Amiri, who started the second golden age in our literature after Navoi's period, gives conflicting evidence in historical sources. Historians and writers who are sympathetic to Amiri put his creative work and creative potential in the first place and wrote many praises in his honor, but in some sources they observe the opposite. For example, when the author of "Majmuat ush-shuaro", Fazliy Namangoniy, who gives information about about seventy poets who developed their profession in Amiri's palace, mentions Amiri with "heavenly man" and hundreds of similar adjectives and descriptions, one of Bukhara's historians, Mirza Muhammad Husayn wrote in his book "History of Nasrullah Khan": "Umar Khan was drunk day and night on the wine of ignorance and was enjoying himself. He was completely ignorant of the affairs of the world. Ismatullabi and Tagikhan used to do whatever they wanted. They placed flame-throwing cannons on the top of the hill on Zindon street, facing the market. Also, Fazli Namangani "Umarnama", Mushrif Isfaragiy "Shahnomayi Nusratpayom", Is'haqkhan Ibrat "History of Fergana", Mirza Olim Mushrif "Ansab us-salatin wa tawarikh ul-khawaqin" Mulla Olim Makhdum Haji, in "History of Turkestan," wrote Amiri in positive terms; On the opposite side, Hakim Khan Tora "Mukhtakhab ut-Tavarikh", Dilshodi Barno "Tarihi Muhojiron", Kavkabiy "Tazkirayi sukhanvaroni Istaravshan" from Bukhara historians had a critical attitude.

In the textbook "History of Uzbek literature" written for higher educational institutions, the court literature of Umar Khan's time is strongly condemned as a reactionary feudal-clerical literature, and the poet's work is an example of ideological poverty and formalism. About him: "He was a feudal ruler given to glory and pleasure, an arrogant and boastful khan who tried to be like Husain Baygara. Amir Omar Khan

gathered many poets around his palace. It is written that most of these poets were flattering poets like Fazli, Nusrat, Ado and Khijlata. However, academician A. Qayumov noted that Umar Khan was "undoubtedly, a very talented poet". In 1926, Sadriddin Ainiy admitted that he had done a lot of work in the world of literature in the collection "Sample Tajik literature" published in 1926. "Fazil and Raso and Ulama and Shuaro had a conversation together. By using them in conversation, he grew in stature day by day, and his voice became famous in the region" - this description given to Umar Khan belongs to the pen of Mushrif, who served in the palace of Kokand khans Mallakhon and Khudoyorkhan in the 19th century. In the words of Polatjon Qayyumi, "regardless of his khanate, we respect him as a great poet from Khokand."

The result:

With the honor of independence, historical justice was restored, and Amir Umar Khan's service in the history of Uzbek statehood, his good deeds as a patron of enlightenment, and his literary legacy as a great poet began to be studied from the point of view of scientific impartiality. New research on this topic has appeared, various sources have been published. Special hours on the study of Amiri's life and work were included in general secondary education and family education programs. The collection "Kashinga tekuzmagil kalamni", materials of the scientific-practical conference held in connection with the 230th anniversary of his birth, as well as Uzbek and Tajik divans were published. In this way, the first steps were taken towards an impartial study of Amiri's personality and activities.

If we look at Amiri's political activity, Umar Khan is pursuing a policy of strengthening power and expanding the territory of the khanate. Takes measures to raise the economy and improve the country; pays special attention to the development of science, culture and literature. "In this heavenly age, scholars, students and people of knowledge are developing, and poetry is respected," writes Ibrat. - In the poem itself, Benazir died, and in "Majmuat ut-shuaro" her eloquence and maturity are evident. Many ditches and canals are dug, as a result of which agriculture flourishes, food products increase, and prices decrease somewhat. According to Mulla Olim Makhdum Haji, Umar Khan "in such a mischief, all the people of Fergana were captivated and enthralled, and he completely put an end to the old and ancient innovations and tyranny, the things forbidden by the Shari'i Sharif." After strengthening the internal power a little, he will also include cities such as Koshgar, Turkestan, Oratepa, Jizzakh, and Tashkent. The people of Tashkent, who fought hard against Olimkhan in those years, welcome Umar Khan with respect. He builds military fortifications such as Okmasjid, Yangikurgan, Qamishkurgan, Julek in the Dashti Kipchak lands. These forts are important in maintaining the strength of Turkestan and guarding trade and caravan routes. According to Umar Khan's order, reforms were also made in religious life. He

returned to Kokhan a number of scholars, fuzalo and famous intellectuals who fled from the oppression of Olim Khan and went to neighboring countries. On his initiative, a mosque and a madrasa will be built in the capital. With the fatwa of scholars, he was given the title "amir ul-muslimin" - emir of Muslims, as well as the nickname "heavenly man". Umar Khan got the right to mint coins in his name and to add his name to the sermon in Friday prayers. As in the Bukhara Emirate, administrative management was introduced, and soon the Kokand Khanate was legalized. Unlike his ancestors, Umar Khan calls himself amir, not a khan. The Khans of Kokhan trace their lineage to Amir Temur through Babur Mirza, and all the Timurids, starting from Temur, declared themselves amirs. In the preface of Umar Khan 's book, he writes: `

Ibrat writes that "In this Umar Khan's age, there were no battles and conflicts, sometimes there was an incident between the palaces of Istaravshan and Oratepa. Although "Umar Khan protected the interests of certain feudal groups during his reign, suppressed intrigues between them, and pursued a cautious policy, the internecine wars did not stop - he did not obey the khanate. recaptured Turkestan, Shymkent and Avliyoota and expanded the territory of the country. However, it cannot be said that Umar Khan always acted with justice during his career and did not allow oppression. For example, the ruler who besieged Oratepa ordered to set fire to the ripe crops in order to break the resistance of the inhabitants of the city and to dry up their crops. "During three days and nights, there was no house in the village, no tree in the garden, no tree in the garden, and no crop in the field, and the mountains and plains were covered with weeds. "They pretended that there was nothing left but stones and soil," Muhammadhakimkhan Tora writes about this in his work "Muntakhab ut-Tawarikh".

Dilshodi criticizes Barno Umar Khan as a ruler, and praises him as a poet. He is glorified by saying "Amir is the king of poetry, Amir is a refuge for his pen pals, And the ghazal Khans are an army, He is a leader at the head of the ranks." while narrating the events of the invasion of Oratepa, he writes, "... being a scientist and a great poet himself, he did not spare a single scientist and poet of this oppressed city." According to him , poetry and kingship do not agree, since Umar Khan is crowned by fate, he is forced to obey the rules of rulership and play the games of this world. In other words, due to his kingdom, Umar Khan did things beyond his control. Because the tradition of ruling has been like this since time immemorial, and despite being a poet, Umar Khan is powerless to go against these customs. Therefore, under the criticism of the poetess, a tone of justification and pity for Umar Khan can be felt. For example, we read in the radifli ghazal "War":

Jahongirliq tamannosi shuncha erurkim,
Bu nomardg`a Amirni ayladi a`zo urush...
Shohdin shoirliq otini yuvdi oxir, ko`rung,

Shohni mot qoldirib, ayladi savdo urush.
 Orzu Barnog`a shulki, bu Amir shoir erur,
 She`r shamshiri ila bo`lg`usi nopaydo urush.

In our opinion, Nadira said the most sincere thoughts about Omar Khan's personality. Because no one knows his human qualities better than his beloved compatriot. Accepting the preface of Nadira's book as a description of Amiri's personality and his family relations, analyzing most of the poems as a derivative of the relationship between these two famous people sheds light on many aspects. Because, while the descriptions and analyzes in Amiri's verses are mostly of a general nature, the fact that Nadira in her poems shows the qualities of the spouse's honesty very delicately, one by one within the framework of oriental manners, is a great reader-poet. one can feel that he is passionately embodied in his eyes. In Nadira's opinion, Umar Khan was a family member of nobility and a fruit of nobility, a teacher of the poor. For this reason, Nadira describes the moments spent with him as happy moments. The poetic description in the prologue serves to poetically revive the aspects of Amiri's personality:

Amiri jahonkim, menga yor edi,
 Aning birla xush davlatim bor edi.
 Iskandar janob-u ulug`shon edi,
 Karampesha Jamshidi davron edi.

Summary:

To conclude, Amir Umar Khan's political activity entered a period of extreme conflict - the period of the division of the khanates into three. He managed to establish peace in difficult conditions, such as the disunity of various social groups, clans and tribes, and subjugate separatist beklis and beklis to a single government. In this regard, we can see that the literary environment of Kokhan, i.e., literature, played the role of a necessary link. Indeed, poet Amiri's literary activity and political activity are compatible with each other like twins.

REFERENCES

1. Fitrat A. Selected works. Volume II. T.: Spirituality, 2006
2. Delighted. Immigrant history; Delighted. Anbar Otin. There are many Uzbek poets. Tashkent: Science, 1994
3. Amiri. Devon. Two volumes. Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2017
4. Kabilova Z. A figure growing up in a golden cradle. Tashkent. Tafakkur Magazine, Issue 2, 2022
5. Haqqul I. Children of literature. Tashkent: Young Guard, 1990
6. Hamidjon Hamidi. Old Eastern Darg alari. (Artistic and scientific films). Tashkent: Sharq, 1999
7. Toshtemirova S. Factors affecting the quality of education and the importance of the education cluster to address them. European journal of research and reflection in educational sciences, 8(4), 151-156
8. and interpretation in literatural classes . Language and literature education. 2020, issue 7.